

ROLE OF MULTILAYER REVIEW MECHANISM IN EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Organizations must adapt to the ever-changing business environment. On the HR front, there have been a lot of changes. The evolution of a multi rater feedback system, generally known as the 360 degree feedback method, has been one of the significant developments. There has been much discussion on whether this methodology should be used for evaluation only, development only, or both. This research study presents an empirically based answer to this topic, hence boosting the effectiveness of the 360 degree feedback mechanism. To uncover characteristics that have a substantial impact on the 360 degree feedback mechanism, exploratory factor analysis was employed. This document also includes recommendations for implementing the 360-degree feedback process effectively. When applied in the correct corporate context and with the expectation of success, multi rater feedback can be maximised.

Keywords: *performance , Employee, Multilevel feedback, Review*

INTRODUCTION

It is critical for a business to assess its employees' performance in order to make various administrative choices such as promotion, salary raises, transfers, and demotions. Simultaneously, it is critical to make employees aware of their strengths and flaws in order for them to grow and develop. Almost every employee is curious in how their work is being evaluated. It essentially emphasises their need to figure out what is going effectively and what has to be changed in order to advance. When an employee is not given feedback, he or she will seek it out on their own. Both learning and motivation are boosted by feedback. Feedback is frequently regarded as a significant motivator for job performance, and the availability of a structured mechanism in place to deliver it leads to higher employee satisfaction. Because the consequences of implementing the incorrect programme can be severe not only for the individual but also for the firm, businesses are growing increasingly concerned about implementing an appropriate feedback system.

When input is received from various sources, it becomes more effective. Evidence suggests that providing timely and frequent feedback has the intended effect of increasing job performance and allowing employees to become more aware of their strengths and developmental needs. Input from numerous sources, such as coworkers, supervisors, and subordinates, is more effective than feedback from a single supervisor. As a result, the 360 degree feedback approach, a new instrument for performance evaluation and development, has emerged.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The goal of this study work is to determine whether 360 degree feedback should be used for appraisal or development. The article also includes recommendations for implementing the 360-degree feedback process effectively.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale. The replies were gathered from 450 people, with 66 of the surveys being incomplete. For the study, 384 replies were used. With the help of Microsoft Excel software, the responses were digitised. Cronbach's alpha statistics were used to test the data for reliability and validity. The data was analysed with the use of ANOVA. An exploratory factor analysis was conducted to determine the significance of the 360-degree feedback review when used for evaluation and development.

FEEDBACK MECHANISM

360 degree feedback, also known as "multi-rater," "multi-source," and "multi-source evaluation," is a management method in which an employee receives feedback from a circle of raters rather than a single supervisor on his job performance, behaviour results, and potential. Superiors, subordinates, peers, clients, suppliers, vendors, and other interested stakeholders with whom he interacts in the course of his job performance are the raters. The raters are the people who give the ratings. The learner is the person whose performance is being evaluated. The learners' own self-evaluation completes the circle. An online/offline questionnaire featuring questions regarding the learners' job performance, behaviour outcomes, and other job-related variables is completed by a group of roughly 10-12 people. With the advancement of technology, online surveys are now being utilised to collect data. The identity of the rater should be anonymous to increase the credibility of the feedback collected, since different research studies have found that respondents may change their ratings if confidentiality of the identity is not ensured due to fear of retaliation. When choosing raters, organisations should be cautious. People in the best position to evaluate a specific sort of job behaviour should be chosen as raters. The collected ratings are then examined, collated, and delivered to the student.

LITERATURE REVIEWED

Aside from appraisal, multi-rater feedback should be employed for progressive reasons. Dalton is a character in the film Dalton (1997).

When conducting performance reviews, the first step that companies should take is to gather extensive information about the individual in question. The obtained data should subsequently be accurately and efficiently shared with the staff. Bohlander, Sherman, Snell, and Sherman (1997)

The 360° approach has been presented as a possible predictor of future performance. Riboldi & Maylett (2007).

The feedback gained through the 360° feedback process has a variety of solutions for all performance-related concerns, and the main reason for this is that it is an unbiased, and relatively simple tool for measuring that provides an unbiased answer. Mukhopadhyaya, Mukhopadhyaya, Mukhopadhyay (2006).

The program's effectiveness is determined by how well it is implemented. The success of a programme can have an impact on an organization's cynicism. It is more effective for an organisation to use multi-rater evaluations for both evaluation and development purposes, according to Atwater, Brett, and Charles (2007). In India, there is a correlation between employee performance appraisal and employee performance, according to Tracy Maylett. According to Singh and Mohanty (2010), there is a link between observed impartiality in performance appraisals and employee satisfaction.

Evaluation

MSF should be utilised for developmental reasons, according to Dalton. It should not be used to evaluate performance or make comparable decisions. If a person understands his current level of performance, he can be more effective when devising a future developmental plan. MSF contributes to the collection of this data. The ratings were shown to be more forgiving and less trustworthy when peers rated colleagues for evaluation rather than developmental objectives. When unfavourable data is collected and used for evaluation purposes, the possibilities of data rejection are significant, and the employee in question will experience a negative behavioural impact. In a feedback context, this also adds to the stress.

Work in organisations is increasingly based on collaboration. To capitalise on the group's skill and combined knowledge, team members must be aware of each other's strengths and developmental areas. MSF can help organisations become more productive by causing targeted behavioural changes. To fully utilise the technique's potential, it should be used for both appraisal and development purposes. It is suggested that 360-degree assessments will fail if the results are not tied to a pay system, as rewards influence behaviour. With the rise of new forms of organisations with a broader range of control, a supervisor-only evaluation technique is no longer considered as an effective means of making various administrative choices such as promotion, transfer, and salary. If 360-degree assessments were used to make administrative decisions, there's a good likelihood that data would be skewed and raters wouldn't give honest feedback.

MSF's full potential, according to Bracken, will not be realised if it is just employed for developmental purposes. If the application of this methodology is restricted, the return on investment will be minimal.

HYPOTHESES

Ha1: 360-degree feedback is widely used in the organisation for performance evaluation.

Data was collected from 430 respondents to examine the above hypotheses. For the data analysis, a total of 391 data points were collected. The data was obtained from Google Drive and entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. After then, the acquired data was put to the test to see if it was reliable and valid. Cronbach's alpha statistics were used to do this.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

An exploratory factor analysis was conducted in order to identify the main elements influencing multi rater feedback. To determine the key aspects that effect 360 degree feedback evaluation, a five-point Likert scale containing 16 assertions is designed. SPSS was used to tabulate the replies received from the respondents using Factor Analysis.

The Cronbach Alpha method was used to assess the scale's dependability, and the result was 0.768, indicating that the data is not skewed and that additional analysis may be carried out without error. In addition, the Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) test was used to determine the precision of the supplied sample, yielding a value of 0.719.

CONCLUSION

People require continual knowledge about their behaviour in order to progress in a company. They need to know what is functioning well and what needs to change. They are given this knowledge through feedback. 360 degree feedback is becoming important in companies because of its capacity to provide structured, in-depth information on present performance and what will be expected of an employee in the future, allowing for the formulation of thorough and appropriate growth plans. Employees believe they are now being paid based on their job performance when this strategy is employed for performance review.

When the 360 degree feedback method is used to help an individual discover his developing areas so that he can work on those areas while also capitalising on his strengths, the technique's worth is maximised. It gathers information from a variety of sources. Each source offers a distinct viewpoint on the employee. This variety of viewpoints can't be reached through any other form of evaluation. Employees have found this to be a motivating tool. Employees were motivated to improve their job performance, according to the study.

The use of the 360-degree feedback method has resulted in the growth of a feedback-giving and feedback-receiving culture. Employees are encouraged to provide and receive feedback, and they actively seek it out.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Workshops addressing concerns with the 360-degree feedback method should be held on a regular basis. Organizations should examine and monitor individual improvement in a time-bound manner based on 360-degree feedback. The input should be given at least once every quarter. The feedback questionnaire should be tailored to the specific demands of the company. Experts from the private and public sectors, as well as academics, may be

invited to discuss topics relating to 360-degree feedback. More effort should be dedicated to training personnel on how to provide, receive, and evaluate feedback. An attempt should be made to persuade the learner to reinforce the desired behaviour while also working on the program's flaws.

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